

Insect Juvenile Hormone Analogues. Part-XVII. Synthesis and Juvenile Hormonal Activity of Undecenyl Ethers and Their Derivatives

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Four substituted-aromatic ethers with undecenyl chain have been prepared by the alkylation of 2-isopropylphenol, 4-isopropylphenol, 5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol and 6-isopropyl-3-methylphenol with 10-undecenyl-1-bromide. These ethers have been modified at the terminal methylene moiety for the preparation of different analogues. Their juvenile hormone activity against *Dysdercus koenigii* Fabricius (red cotton bug) is described.

A large number of aromatic ethers of geraniol and citronellol and their homologues show moderate activity on *Dysdercus koenigii* Fabricius¹⁻⁴. Some new undecenyl aromatic ethers for the exploration of the effect of different substituents on the aromatic ring and conversion to their respective epoxy, dichloromethylene, dibromomethylene and tertiary carbinol derivatives, a variety of compounds are reported to study their structure-activity relationship.

2-Isopropylphenol, 4-isopropylphenol, 5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol and 6-isopropyl-3-methylphenol were alkylated with 10-undecenyl-1-bromide in refluxing acetone containing anhydrous K_2CO_3 to afford the ethers (1-4), which on treatment with equimolar amount of *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in anhydrous methylene chloride yielded the mono-epoxy derivatives (5-8).

Reaction of the ether (1) in chloroform with aqueous NaOH in the presence of triethylbenzylammonium chloride⁵ as phase transfer catalyst produced 1-(2'-isopropylphenoxy)-10,11-dichloromethylene undecane (9) in 40% yield. Under similar reaction conditions, the ethers (2-4) furnished the dichloromethylene derivatives (10-12). Treatment of the ethers (1-4) with bromoform and triethylbenzylammonium chloride in aqueous NaOH have the dibromomethylene derivatives (13-16) under the same reaction conditions. The ethers (1-4), on mercuriation-demercuration⁷ yielded alcohols (17-20). Ir spectra of these alcohols showed the absence of methylenic double bond and the presence of OH grouping at 910 and 3350 cm^{-1} , respectively. On oxidation with pyridinium chlorochromate⁸, the alcohols furnished the ketones (21-24), showing λ_{max} at 1710 cm^{-1} (C=O). These ketones, in turn on Grignard reaction with methyl iodide, ethyl bromide and isopropyl iodide yielded the tertiary carbinols (25-36), respectively. These were characterised by their ir, pmr and analytical data.

(25-36)			
	$\frac{R}{i-Pr}$	$\frac{R'}{H}$	$\frac{R''}{H}$
1, 5, 9, 13, 17, 21, 25, 29, 33	$\frac{R}{i-Pr}$	$\frac{R'}{H}$	$\frac{R''}{H}$
2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22, 26, 30, 34	H	H	<i>i</i> -Pr
3, 7, 11, 15, 19, 23, 27, 31, 35	CH ₃	<i>i</i> -Pr	H
4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36	<i>i</i> -Pr	CH ₃	H
25-28	$\frac{R'''}{OH}$		
29-32	C ₂ H ₅		
33-36	<i>i</i> -Pr		

All the compounds (tlc-pure) were tested for their juvenile hormone (JH) activity against

Dysdercus koenigii Fabricius according to the procedure reported in the literature^{9,10}. Farnesyl methyl ether was used as standard (JH score=4.00)¹¹. The scoring results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—JH ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS

Number of insects used=10, does=1% in acetone (6 μ l)

Compd. no.	Dead	Activity response					Activity index
		0	1	2	3	4	
1	0	1	3	0	2	4	2.50
2	0	0	3	2	2	3	2.50
3	0	1	3	0	2	4	2.50
4	0	2	3	2	0	3	1.90
5	1	0	2	0	3	4	3.00
6	1	0	0	1	3	6	3.56
7	1	0	3	0	2	4	2.80
8	1	0	2	1	1	5	3.00
9	0	0	2	0	2	6	3.20
10	0	0	0	1	0	9	3.80
11	0	0	0	0	1	9	3.90
12	1	0	0	2	1	6	3.40
13	0	1	1	0	1	7	3.20
14	1	0	2	0	1	6	3.20
15	0	0	1	2	0	7	3.30
16	0	0	2	2	0	6	3.00
25	0	0	1	2	2	5	3.10
26	0	0	1	0	0	9	3.70
27	0	4	3	1	2	0	1.10
28	1	3	3	1	2	0	1.22
29	1	1	2	0	1	5	2.78
30	0	0	4	0	0	6	2.80
31	1	4	4	1	0	0	0.66
32	0	2	5	2	1	0	1.20
33	1	2	3	1	3	0	1.56
34	0	0	1	0	1	8	3.60
35	0	2	6	1	1	0	1.10
36	1	1	4	2	2	0	1.55

The activity indices show that the ethers (1-4) are moderately active in the range of 1.90 to 2.50. The epoxy, dichloromethylene and dibromomethylene derivatives are more active than the parent ethers. The maximum activity of these derivatives is 3.90. The tertiary carbinols show moderate to high activity in comparison to the parent ether.

The spectral data of the ethers, epoxides, dichloromethylene, dibromomethylene and tertiary carbinol derivatives are consistent with their structures. Spectral and characterisation data of compounds (2-4, 6-8, 10-12, 14-16, 18-20, 22-24, 26-28, 30-32, 33-36) are given in Table 2. The boiling points of the dichloromethylene, dibromomethylene and oxirane derivatives could not be recorded due to paucity of the samples.

Experimental

All the m.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction b.p. 60-80°. Tlc was carried out on silica gel containing 15% gypsum; visualisation agent being iodine. Ir spectra were recorded as thin smears for liquids and in nujol for solids on a Perkin-Elmer 337 and 377 spectrophotometers with sodium chloride using thin films. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer in carbon tetrachloride

using TMS as an internal standard. Organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate unless otherwise stated.

10-Undecenyl-2'-isopropylphenyl ether (1): A mixture of 2-isopropylphenol (7.92 g, 60 mmol), anhydrous potassium carbonate (80 g) and 10-undecenyl-1-bromide (13.98 g, 60 mmol) in dry acetone (350 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The contents were cooled, filtered and the filtrate concentrated. The residue was taken up in ether, washed with 10% aqueous NaOH and water, and the organic layer dried. Removal of the solvent and distillation of the residue under reduced pressure gave 1 (10.2 g, 60%), b.p. 142-45°/2 mm (Found: C, 83.35; H, 11.12. C₂₀H₃₂O requires C, 83.27; H, 11.18%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2900, 1660, 1610 1510, 1460, 1310, 1210, 1165, 1100, 1040, 910 and 750 cm⁻¹; δ 1.15-2.23 (22H, satd. -CH₂- and -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂), 3.35 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 7.5Hz, CH₂-O-Ar), 5.0 (2H, H₂C=CH), 5.85 (1H, m, H₂C=CH-CH₂) and 6.6-7.25 (4H, Ar-H).

Similarly, 4-isopropylphenol, 5-isopropyl-2-methylphenol and 6-isopropyl-3-methylphenol were alkylated with 10-undecenyl-1-bromide to yield the ether 2-4, respectively. The characterisation data of these compounds are given in Table 2.

10,11-Epoxyundecenyl-2'-isopropyl phenyl ether (5): To a well stirred ice-cold solution of ether (1; 0.72 g, 2.5 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (75 ml) was added *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (0.47 g, 2.75 mmol) in anhydrous methylene chloride (25 ml) dropwise. After the addition was complete, the mixture was stirred for 45 min at 0° and 30 min at room temperature and poured into water. The organic layer was separated, and washed successively with saturated NaHCO₃ solution and cold water, dried, the solvent removed *in vacuo* and the residue chromatographed over florisil to give 5 (0.266 g, 35%) (Found: C, 78.97; H, 10.55. C₂₀H₃₂O₂ requires C, 78.89; H, 10.59%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2950, 1600, 1460, 1400, 1360, 1255, 1210, 1165, 1100, 1050, 840 and 760 cm⁻¹; δ 1.2-1.9 (22H, satd. -CH₂- and -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂), 2.3 (1H, m, H₂C-CH-CH₂), 2.67 (2H, H₂C-CH-CH₂), 3.4 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH₃)₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 7.5Hz, CH₂-O-Ar) and 6.65-7.35 (4H, Ar-H).

Similarly, 2-4 were converted to oxiranes on treatment with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid in equimolar amounts to afford 6-8. The characterisation data of the oxiranes are given in Table 2.

1-(2'-Isopropylphenoxy)-10,11-dichloromethyleneundecane (9): A solution of ether (1; 0.72 g, 2 mmol) in chloroform (8 ml) was treated with triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.115 g, 0.5 mmol) (prepared from equimolar triethylamine and benzyl chloride in acetone). The mixture was stirred until the salt dissolved. Aqueous NaOH (1.25 ml, 50%) was added and the stirring continued for further 3 days. Water was introduced in the reaction mixture, the product extracted with chloroform and the extract dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. After removing the solvent, the residue was chromato-

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISATION OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	B.p. °C/mm	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
				C	H	X*
2	165-67/2-3	59	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O	82.95 (83.27)	11.25 (11.18)	—
3	150-55/2-3	58	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O	83.44 (83.38)	11.21 (11.33)	—
4	148-50/1-2	61	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O	83.20 (83.38)	11.15 (11.33)	—
6	—	33	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂	79.00 (78.89)	10.37 (10.59)	—
7	—	32	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.06 (79.19)	10.72 (10.76)	—
8	—	30	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.32 (79.19)	10.50 (10.76)	—
10	—	38	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ OCl ₂	68.12 (68.00)	8.49 (8.63)	19.26 (19.14)
11	—	39	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ OCl ₂	68.72 (68.57)	8.69 (8.83)	18.36 (18.44)
12	—	41	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ OCl ₂	68.49 (69.57)	8.81 (8.83)	18.49 (18.44)
13	—	42	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ OBr ₂	55.00 (54.80)	6.92 (7.00)	34.93 (34.80)
14	—	43	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ OBr ₂	54.63 (54.80)	6.92 (7.00)	34.97 (34.80)
15	—	40	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ OBr ₂	55.87 (55.70)	7.05 (7.20)	33.93 (33.80)
16	—	42	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ OBr ₂	55.62 (55.70)	7.10 (7.20)	33.78 (33.80)
18	170-72/1-2	60	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂	78.57 (78.38)	11.02 (11.19)	—
19	175-80/1-2	62	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.54 (78.69)	11.50 (11.32)	—
20	170-72/1-2	61	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.81 (78.69)	11.35 (11.32)	—
22	165-67/2-3	64	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂	79.05 (78.89)	10.51 (10.59)	—
23	142-45/1-2	63	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.10 (79.19)	10.88 (10.76)	—
24	155-60/2-3	63	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.28 (79.19)	10.80 (10.76)	—
26	170-72/1-2	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.73 (78.69)	11.41 (11.32)	—
27	185-90/3-4	72	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.75 (78.98)	11.57 (11.45)	—
28	175-80/1-2	67	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.10 (78.98)	11.90 (11.45)	—
29	167-70/1-2	68	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.87 (78.98)	11.42 (11.45)	—
30	175-80/1-2	67	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.15 (78.98)	11.42 (11.45)	—
31	185-90/2-3	69	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.10 (79.25)	11.65 (11.57)	—
32	180-82/2-3	68	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.37 (79.25)	11.39 (11.57)	—
33	180-85/1-2	71	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.22 (79.25)	11.68 (11.57)	—
34	35**	67	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.42 (79.25)	11.39 (11.57)	—
35	190-95/1-2	69	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.42 (79.50)	11.79 (11.68)	—
36	185-87/1-2	67	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.72 (79.50)	11.53 (11.68)	—

* Halogen. ** M.p.

graphed over florasil to afford **9** (0.36 g, 40%) (Found: C, 67.85; H, 8.87; Cl, 19.1. C₁₂H₁₂OCl₂ requires C, 68.0; H, 8.63; Cl, 19.0%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2900, 1580, 1450, 1380, 1300, 1250, 1160, 1120, 1050, 830 and 745 cm⁻¹; δ 1.1-1.8 (25H, H₂C-CH-CH₂, satd. -CH₂- and -Ar-CH(CH₂)₂), 3.4 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH₂)₂), 3.95 (2H, t, *J* 7.5Hz, -CH₂-O-Ar) and 6.6-7.4 (4H, Ar-H).

Similarly, dichloromethylene derivatives (**10-12**) of ethers (**2-4**) were prepared by stirring with triethylbenzylammonium chloride and 50% NaOH in chloroform. Their characterisation data is given in Table 2.

Dibromomethylene derivatives (**13-16**) from parent ethers (**1-4**) were prepared in a similar method described above using bromoform instead of chloro-

form. Their characterisation data is given in Table 2.

11-(2'-Isopropylphenoxy)-2-undecanol (17): To a yellow solution of mercuric(II) acetate (7.14 g, 24 mmol) in water (16 ml) and THF (40 ml) was added 10-undecenyl-2'-isopropyl phenyl ether (1; 5.68 g, 20 mmol) with stirring at room temperature. The yellow colour of the solution disappeared in a few minutes after the addition 1. The reaction mixture was stirred for another 2 h, cooled and alkaline sodium borohydride (0.4 g in 20 ml of 3N NaOH) added. The aqueous layer was saturated with NaCl after metallic mercury settled down. The organic layer was extracted with ether and the combined organic extracts dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue chromatographed over neutral alumina afforded 7 (3.94 g, 60%), b.p. 182-85°/2-3 mm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3350, 2920, 1600, 1470, 1400, 1300, 1250, 1210, 1130, 1100, 1050, 935 and 750 cm^{-1} .

In presence of pyridinium chlorochromate in anhydrous methylene chloride 11-(2'-isopropylphenoxy)-2-undecanol was oxidised⁸ to 11-(2'-isopropylphenoxy)-2-undecanone (21) (65%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2940, 1710, 1600, 1490, 1380, 1245, 1150, 1090, 1050 and 750 cm^{-1} .

11-(2'-Isopropylphenoxy)-2-methyl undecanol (25): To a well stirred solution of methylmagnesium iodide prepared from Mg (0.6 g) and methyl iodide (2.4 g) in anhydrous ether (150 ml) was added 11-(2'-isopropylphenoxy)-2-undecanone (21; 2.25 g, 7.5 mmol) at low temperature. The contents were left overnight, refluxed for 1 h and decomposed with ice-cold solution of NH_4Cl . The organic layer was separated and dried. Removal of the solvent gave the crude product which was chromatographed to yield the tertiary carbinol 25 (1.77 g, 75%), b.p. 165-70°/1-2 mm; $\nu_{\max}$ 3350, 2900, 1580, 1450, 1380, 1300, 1250, 1160, 1100, 1050 and 750 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.1-1.9 (29H, satd. - CH_2 -, CH_3 and OH), 3.35 (1H, m, -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, - CH_2 -O-Ar) and 6.65-7.25 (4H, Ar-H).

Similarly, the ether 1 was converted to the tertiary carbinol with ethylmagnesium bromide and isopropylmagnesium iodide to afford 29 and 33, respectively. The ethers 2-4 were converted to their corresponding tertiary carbinol with CH_3MgI , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{MgBr}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHMgI}$ to yield 26-28, 30-32 and 34-36, respectively. The characterisation data of these carbinols are given in Table 2. Ir and ^1H nmr spectral data of the compounds are provided in Table 3.

TABLE 3—IR AND NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	$\nu_{\max}$ cm^{-1}	δ
2	2880, 1600, 1510, 1460, 1300, 1255, 1190, 1040, 915, 890	1.1-2.15 (22H, - CH_2 - and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.8 (1H, m, -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.85 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH_2 -O-Ar), 4.8-5.1 (2H, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 5.75 (1H, m, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 6.9 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
3	2870, 2830, 1630, 1595, 1560, 1485, 1440, 1400, 1240, 1155, 1120, 1085, 1205, 985, 900, 840, 800, 715	1.1-1.36 (20H, satd. - CH_2 - and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.96-2.1 (2H, allylic - CH_2 -), 2.17-2.3 (3H, 2s, -Ar- OCH_3), 3.33 (1H, m, -Ar $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH_2 -O-Ar), 4.9-5.13 (2H, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 5.8 (1H, m, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 6.76-7.15 (3H, Ar-H)
4	2920, 2850, 1610, 1590, 1510, 1460, 1430, 1360, 1275, 1180, 1110, 1045, 915, 815	1.15-1.55 (18H, satd. - CH_2 - and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.6-2.1 (4H, CH_2 -, CH_2 -O-Ar and allylic - CH_2 -), 2.3 (3H, s, -Ar- OCH_3), 3.3 (1H, m, -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.9 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH_2 -O-Ar), 4.82-5.1 (2H, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}$), 5.75 (1H, m, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 6.6-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
6	2870, 1585, 1480, 1435, 1360, 1270, 1225, 1165, 1020, 820, 780	1.1-1.9 (22H, satd. - CH_2 - and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.2 (1H, m, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 2.7 (3H, m, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{OH}$ and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.85 (2H, t, J 6Hz, - CH_2 -O-Ar), 6.85 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
7	2900, 2840, 1650, 1600, 1580, 1450, 1310, 1270, 1185, 1145, 1110, 1045, 925, 820, 795, 730	1.0-1.55 (22H, satd. - CH_2 - and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.1-2.35 (4H, -Ar- CH_2 and $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 2.73 (2H, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.33 (1H, m, -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH_2 -O-Ar), 6.6-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
8	2920, 2850, 1600, 1500, 1460, 1430, 1360, 1270, 1180, 1035, 815, 790	1.1-1.92 (22H, satd. - CH_2 - and -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.0 (1H, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 2.3 (3H, s, -Ar- OCH_3), 2.67 (2H, $\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.23 (1H, m, -Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH_2 -O-Ar), 6.6-7.05 (3H, Ar-H)

(Table 3 contd.)

10	2920, 2840, 1600, 1580, 1500, 1460, 1480, 1300, 1275, 1195, 1185, 1050, 860, 820, 755	1.2-1.8 (25H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{COCl}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{---CH---CH}_2 \end{array}$), 2.83 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.87 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.83 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
11	2900, 2840, 1610, 1580, 1460, 1430, 1275, 1195, 1135, 1050, 820, 755	1.1-1.86 (25H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{COCl}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{H}_2\text{C---CH-} \end{array}$), 2.15-2.3 (3H, 2s, -Ar-CH ₃), 3.3 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.97 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.66-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
12	2910, 2845, 1600, 1460, 1390, 1310, 1300, 1250, 1205, 1160, 1130, 1100, 1050, 860, 820, 750	1.2-1.85 (25H, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ , satd. -CH ₂ - and $\begin{array}{c} \text{COCl}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{H}_2\text{C---CH-} \end{array}$), 2.3 (3H, s, -Ar-CH ₃), 3.27 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.92 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.66-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
13	2920, 2840, 1600, 1460, 1380, 1300, 1260, 1160, 1120, 1060, 750	1.1-1.8 (25H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{CBr}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{H}_2\text{C---CH-} \end{array}$), 3.3 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.6-7.2 (4H, Ar-H)
14	2900, 1600, 1580, 1500, 1470, 1420, 1305, 1275, 1190, 1135, 1050, 860, 820	1.2-1.85 (25H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{CBr}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{H}_2\text{C---CH-} \end{array}$), 2.3 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.9 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.85 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
15	2910, 2840, 1595, 1500, 1480, 1450, 1420, 1270, 1185, 1145, 1110, 1050, 855, 820, 750	1.0-1.86 (25H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{CBr}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{H}_2\text{C---CH-CH}_2 \end{array}$), 2.15-2.3 (3H, 2s, -Ar-CH ₃), 3.3 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.66-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
16	2900, 2840, 1600, 1460, 1300, 1250, 1130, 1095, 1050, 750	1.1-1.85 (25H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and $\begin{array}{c} \text{CBr}_2 \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{H}_2\text{C---CH-} \end{array}$), 2.3 (3H, s, -Ar-CH ₃), 3.25 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.66-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
18	3350, 2900, 1620, 1540, 1520, 1470, 1390, 1350, 1300, 1260, 1190, 1150, 1070, 1030, 940, 840, 815, 730	—
19	3340, 2910, 1610, 1590, 1470, 1380, 1300, 1260, 1180, 1080, 1030, 945, 825, 740	—
20	3350, 2900, 1480, 1390, 1300, 1270, 1195, 1060, 940, 820, 750	—
22	2900, 2840, 1710, 1610, 1480, 1385, 1360, 1300, 1270, 1190, 1070, 1040, 935, 820, 740	—
23	2910, 1720, 1600, 1595, 1460, 1385, 1300, 1280, 1170, 1060, 820, 750	—
24	2900, 1710, 1610, 1590, 1485, 1380, 1300, 1260, 1190, 1050, 945, 840, 750	—
26	3400, 2950, 2850, 1610, 1580, 1510, 1480, 1390, 1300, 1255, 1190, 835	1.15-1.68 (28H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and (CH ₃) ₂ C(OH)-CH ₂), 1.75 (1H, br s, -OH exch. with D ₂ O), 2.85 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.85 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.85 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
27	3380, 2950, 2860, 1620, 1590, 1510, 1490, 1440, 1390, 1310, 1270, 1180, 1110, 1050, 945, 850, 820	1.07-1.55 (29H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and (CH ₃) ₂ C(OH)-CH ₂ -), 2.17-2.26 (3H, 2s, -Ar-CH ₃), 3.27 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.6-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
28	3400, 2920, 2850, 1610, 1590, 1460, 1420, 1370, 1305, 1275, 1180, 1105, 1045, 850, 815	1.13-1.98 (29H, satd. -CH ₂ -, (H ₂ O) ₂ C(OH)-CH ₂ and -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 2.27 (3H, s, -Ar-CH ₃), 3.2 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.9 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar); 6.6-6.97 (3H, Ar-H)
29	3350, 2950, 1590, 1460, 1380, 1300, 1260, 1160, 1100, 1050, 755	0.87 (3H, t, J 6Hz, H ₂ C-CH ₂ -C(OH)), 1.05-1.95 (28H, satd. -CH ₂ -, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂ and H ₂ C-CH ₂ -C(OH)-CH ₂), 3.35 (1H, m, -Ar-CH(CH ₃) ₂), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, CH ₂ -O-Ar), 6.97 (4H, m, Ar-H)

(Table 3 contd.)

30	3400, 2950, 2870, 1610, 1590, 1510, 1490, 1390, 1300, 1260, 1190, 1050, 835, 790	0.89 (3H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}(\text{OH})$), 1.2-1.9 (28H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $\text{H}_2\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 2.85 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.9 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.87 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
31	3400, 2950, 2850, 1620, 1590, 1510, 1470, 1430, 1390, 1310, 1275, 1185, 1110, 1060, 855, 820	0.87 (3H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{H}_2\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}(\text{OH})$), 1.0-1.86 (28H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 2.15-2.3 (3H, 2s, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.27 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.6-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
32	3400, 2920, 2850, 1620, 1590, 1500, 1460, 1390, 1305, 1275, 1180, 1105, 815, 790	0.85 (3H, t, J 7.5Hz, $\text{H}_2\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}(\text{OH})$), 1.05-1.9 (28H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, Ar- $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $\text{H}_2\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 2.25 (3H, s, Ar- CH_2), 3.25 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.9 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.63-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
33	3360, 2900, 2850, 1600, 1450, 1380, 1300, 1250, 1100, 1055, 790, 750	1.1-1.92 (33H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CH}-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 3.95 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.97 (4H, m, Ar-H)
34	3360, 2920, 1610, 1510, 1480, 1390, 1305, 1260, 1195, 1150, 1035, 940, 840, 795	1.12-1.92 (33H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $(\text{H}_2\text{C})_2\text{CH}-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 2.85 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.88 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.9 (4H, ABq, Ar-H)
35	3400, 2920, 2850, 1610, 1590, 1500, 1470, 1420, 1380, 1310, 1270, 1185, 855, 820	1.05-1.86 (33H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $(\text{H}_2\text{C})_2\text{CH}-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 2.15-2.3 (3H, 2s, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.27 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.95 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.66-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)
36	3410, 2910, 2850, 1605, 1590, 1460, 1380, 1300, 1275, 1180, 815, 785	1.1-1.9 (33H, satd. $-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$, and $(\text{H}_2\text{C})_2\text{CH}-(\text{CH}_2)\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{CH}_2$), 2.3 (3H, s, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}_2$), 3.25 (1H, m, $-\text{Ar}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_2$), 3.92 (2H, t, J 6Hz, $\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\text{Ar}$), 6.65-7.0 (3H, Ar-H)

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References

- M. SCHWARZ, P. E. SONNET and N. WAKABAYASHI, *Science*, 1970, 167, 191.
- M. SCHWARZ, N. WAKABAYASHI and P. E. SONNET, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1970, 63, 1858.
- L. M. SCHOONHOVEN, *Ann. Rev. Entomol.*, 1968, 13, 115.
- H. SCHULZ and I. SPRUNG, *Angew. Chem.*, 1969, 81, 258.
- I. F. FIESER and M. FIESER, "Reagents for Organic Syntheses", John Wiley, New York, 1967, Vol. 1, p. 136.
- R. IKAN, A. MARKUS and Z. GOLDSCHMIDT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 2423.
- C. S. SUBRAMANIAM, P. Z. THOMAS, V. R. MAMDAPUR and M. S. CHADHA, *Synthesis*, 1978, 468.
- E. J. COREY and J. W. SUGGS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 2647.
- BRANSKY-W. R. WILLIAMS, *Bull. Entomol. Res.*, 1971, 61, 41.
- O. P. VIG, I. R. TREHAN, G. L. KAD, R. K. DHAWAN and M. S. GREWAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, 19, 683.
- K. SLAMA, M. ROMANUK and F. SORM, "Insect Hormones and Bioanalogs", Springer-Verlag, New York, 1974, p. 183.